

Pocket LiDAR for Dimensional Measurement of Precast Concrete Panels

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the feasibility of pocket LiDAR as a low-cost solution for dimensional quality control (QC) of precast concrete elements. Traditional methods rely on manual tape measurements, which are labor-intensive and prone to human error. High-precision technologies such as terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) are expensive and difficult to operate. To bridge this gap, this research assesses pocket LiDAR based on comparisons with TLS and tape measurements through controlled experiments. Point cloud data of a concrete slab specimen were collected in both pre-casting and post-casting stages using TLS and an iPhone LiDAR system. The datasets were evaluated in terms of point cloud fidelity, dimensional accuracy, and compliance with industry tolerances. Results show that pocket LiDAR achieved a root mean square error (RMSE) of 5.5 mm in rebar position measurements compared to TLS, significantly outperforming tape measurements (45.8 mm RMSE). For concrete dimensional measurements, pocket LiDAR demonstrated comparable accuracy to tape measurements. Compliance analysis further indicated that pocket LiDAR can reliably identify most tolerance violations in rebar position and concrete dimension, although minor discrepancies were observed in borderline cases. Overall, pocket LiDAR demonstrates strong potential as a practical alternative for rapid and automated QC in precast construction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional quality control (QC) of the dimensions of precast concrete (PC) elements relies heavily on manual inspections and tape measurements, which are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and susceptible to human errors. While high-precision sensing technologies such as Terrestrial Laser Scanning provide an alternative, their adoption in precast plants is limited due to high equipment costs and complex operational workflows. Terrestrial Laser Scanners (TLS) typically range from approximately \$20,000 to over \$100,000 depending on performance specifications (Aniwa, 2020).

Pocket LiDAR has emerged as a low cost, but accurate solution for automating dimensional QC of both concrete geometry and reinforcement bar (rebar) placement. Pocket LiDAR systems can be implemented using built-in LiDAR sensors in consumer devices (e.g., smartphones or tablets), eliminating the need for additional hardware investment if such devices are already available. For higher-accuracy applications, RTK-enhanced configurations cost in the range of \$5,000–\$7,000, providing a more accessible alternative for QC applications (E38 Survey Solutions, n.d.).

This study assessed the pocket LiDAR in three aspects: point cloud fidelity, dimensional accuracy, and compliance with industry tolerances. Experimentation was conducted to collect point cloud data from a concrete slab specimen using TLS and pocket LiDAR. By benchmarking datasets from pocket LiDAR against TLS ground truth, this study assesses whether the resolution of pocket LiDAR is sufficient to meet tolerance requirements for precast components. Tape measurements were also taken and included in the comparisons. While the current assessment uses a standard concrete slab, the findings inspire the consideration of pocket LiDAR for QC applications across a broad range of precast concrete elements such as Mechanically Stabilized Earth (MSE) wall panels, bridge deck panels, girders, and piles.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND DATA COLLECTION

The feasibility assessment focuses on comparing data quality and acquisition efficiency between professional-grade TLS and consumer-grade pocket LiDAR. Experimental data were collected at the Bowen Laboratory under controlled conditions.

Seven concrete slabs with identical rebar displacement configurations were fabricated. Although the slabs included varying supplementary reinforcements, this study focused on the specimen without supplementary reinforcement to minimize occlusion and better capture the main reinforcement bars. Data collection was conducted in both pre-casting and post-casting stages. Figure 1 shows the data collection environment and the drawings of the target slab. Three measurement methods were used to evaluate precision and efficiency. For TLS, the FARO Focus 3D X 330 (FARO Technologies, n.d.), was used to establish the ground truth. An iPhone 16 Pro utilizing its integrated Camera and LiDAR sensor served as the pocket LiDAR system, with Pix4Dcatch employed for data collection and registration. A physical tape was used to record baseline dimensions and rebar positions as in the current practice.

Figure 1. Data collection at Bowen Lab: pre- and post-casting (left); drawings (right).

Using TLS, two high-resolution scans (1/1 resolution, 4x quality) were obtained over approximately 4 hours and registered with a mean point error of 2.0 mm. After manually cropping the target slab region, the

resulting benchmark datasets consist of approximately 85 million and 81 million points for the pre-casting and post-casting states, respectively, providing a geometric gold standard for the target slab. Pocket LiDAR data were captured in approximately 3 minutes. After cropping the same region of interest, the resulting point clouds contained approximately 1.6 million and 0.8 million points for the pre-casting and post-casting states, respectively.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The performance of Pocket LiDAR was assessed in three aspects: point cloud fidelity, dimensional accuracy, and compliance with specification tolerances.

3.1 Point Cloud Fidelity: TLS vs. Pocket LiDAR

The comparison focuses on the pre-casting state due to its higher geometric complexity, as shown in Figure 2. Both point clouds were downsampled using a voxel size of 1 mm, resulting in 820,152 points for TLS and 778,854 points for pocket LiDAR. The Iterative Closest Point (ICP) registration yielded a fitness of 0.547 and a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 2.8 mm. Correspondence analysis was performed using a 5 mm distance threshold. The spatial distribution of corresponding and non-corresponding points is illustrated in Figure 3, and quantitative results are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2. Point clouds generated from TLS (left) and Pocket LiDAR (right) in the pre-casting state.

Figure 3. Correspondence visualization between TLS (left) and pocket LiDAR (right) point clouds. Corresponding points are shown in green, and non-corresponding points are shown in red.

Table 1. Number of inliers and outliers after point cloud registration.

Technology	Inliers	Outliers	Total
TLS	441,683	378,469	820,152
Pocket LiDAR	465,210	313,644	778,854

3.2 Dimensional Measurement

Rebar positions and concrete dimensions were measured using TLS, pocket LiDAR, and tape. The results are presented in Tables 2 and 3. Figure 4 illustrates the notation system, where S_n denotes the n^{th} short rebar (aligned in the transverse direction) and L_m denotes the m^{th} long rebar (aligned in the longitudinal direction). The X-axis represents the longitudinal direction of the slab, and Y-axis represents the transverse direction. Depth 1–4 denote thickness measurements taken at the four corners of the slab.

Figure 4. Notations for rebars and concrete slab dimensions.

For rebar position measurements, pocket LiDAR achieved an RMSE of 5.5 mm relative to TLS, significantly outperforming tape measurements, which exhibited an RMSE of 45.8 mm. This indicates that pocket LiDAR provides substantially improved accuracy over traditional manual methods for determining the quality of rebar placement.

For concrete dimensional measurements, pocket LiDAR and tape measurements showed comparable accuracy. This is attributed to the relatively simple rectangular geometry of the concrete elements, wherein manual measurement remains effective.

Table 2. Rebar position measurements at intersections and deviations relative to TLS.

	TLS	PL	TM	[TLS] - [PL]	[TLS] - [TM]
x (S0, L0)	0.1910	0.2032	0.1910	-0.0123	-
x (S1, L0)	0.4731	0.4775	0.5243	-0.0044	-0.0512
x (S2, L0)	0.6151	0.6197	0.6736	-0.0046	-0.0585
x (S3, L0)	0.8049	0.8090	0.8498	-0.0041	-0.0449
x (S4, L0)	1.0056	1.0095	1.0514	-0.0038	-0.0457
x (S5, L0)	1.1913	1.1925	1.2276	-0.0012	-0.0363
x (S6, L0)	1.3431	1.3413	1.3721	0.0018	-0.0290
x (S7, L0)	1.6913	1.6875	1.7404	0.0038	-0.0490
x (S8, L0)	1.8305	1.8282	1.8943	0.0023	-0.0638
x (S9, L0)	2.0155	2.0114	2.0626	0.0041	-0.0471
x (S10, L0)	2.2264	2.2226	2.2658	0.0038	-0.0394
x (S11, L0)	2.4088	2.4107	2.4436	-0.0018	-0.0348
x (S12, L0)	2.5504	2.5474	2.6119	0.0030	-0.0615
x (S13, L0)	2.8966	2.8868	2.8945	0.0098	0.0021
x (S0, L3)	0.1939	0.2066	0.1939	-0.0127	-
x (S1, L3)	0.4769	0.4880	0.5448	-0.0111	-0.0679
x (S2, L3)	0.6455	0.6533	0.6861	-0.0078	-0.0406
x (S3, L3)	0.8227	0.8296	0.8702	-0.0069	-0.0475
x (S4, L3)	1.0262	1.0328	1.0813	-0.0066	-0.0551
x (S5, L3)	1.1947	1.2001	1.2687	-0.0055	-0.0740
x (S6, L3)	1.3492	1.3562	1.4068	-0.0070	-0.0575
x (S7, L3)	1.7170	1.7211	1.7576	-0.0041	-0.0407
x (S8, L3)	1.8626	1.8650	1.9068	-0.0024	-0.0442
x (S9, L3)	2.0394	2.0413	2.0926	-0.0019	-0.0531
x (S10, L3)	2.2358	2.2373	2.2942	-0.0016	-0.0584
x (S11, L3)	2.4149	2.4087	2.4847	0.0062	-0.0697
x (S12, L3)	2.5645	2.5603	2.6276	0.0043	-0.0630
x (S13, L3)	2.9013	2.8959	2.9038	0.0054	-0.0025
y (S0, L0)	0.1549	0.1524	0.1549	0.0025	-
y (S0, L1)	0.3423	0.3382	0.3549	0.0041	-0.0126
y (S0, L2)	0.7140	0.7112	0.7200	0.0028	-0.0060
y (S0, L3)	0.9104	0.9054	0.9169	0.0051	-0.0065
y (S13, L0)	0.1371	0.1393	0.1371	-0.0022	-
y (S13, L1)	0.3227	0.3198	0.3403	0.0029	-0.0177

y (S13, L2)	0.7049	0.7036	0.6975	0.0013	0.0073
y (S13, L3)	0.8910	0.8880	0.8991	0.0030	-0.0081
RMSE	-	-	-	0.0055	0.0458

Bold font indicates values in the TM column that were derived from TLS data, as the spacing from the formwork edge to rebars S0 and L0 was not directly measured in the experiment. (PL: pocket LiDAR; TM: tape measure)

Table 3. Concrete dimension measurements and deviations relative to TLS.

	TLS	PL	TM	[TLS] - [PL]	[TLS] - [TM]
Length 1	3.1150	3.1284	3.1258	-0.0134	-0.0108
Length 2	3.1163	3.1299	3.1258	-0.0136	-0.0095
Width 1	1.0627	1.0679	1.0668	-0.0051	-0.0041
Width 2	1.0608	1.0625	1.0668	-0.0018	-0.0060
Depth 1	0.4047	0.4082	0.4088	-0.0035	-0.0041
Depth 2	0.4068	0.4024	0.4072	0.0045	-0.0004
Depth 3	0.4068	0.4050	0.4080	0.0018	-0.0012
Depth 4	0.4049	0.4064	0.4072	-0.0015	-0.0023
RMSE	-	-	-	0.0073	0.0059

3.3 Compliance Checking

A compliance checking was conducted by comparing measured values against design specifications and industry tolerances. The allowable tolerance for rebar placement is ± 12.7 mm (ACI, 2010), while concrete dimensional tolerances are ± 12.7 mm for length and ± 6.3 mm for width and depth (PCI, 2024). Table 4 summarizes the compliance results obtained using TLS and pocket LiDAR. A discrepancy was observed for rebars S3 and S4: TLS reported deviations of 9.9 mm and 10.2 mm, respectively (within tolerance), whereas pocket LiDAR reported deviations of 16.8 mm for both cases (exceeding tolerance). Tape measure results indicated that all rebar positions were non-compliant, which may be attributed to cumulative measurement errors inherent in measuring spacing between rebars. For concrete slab dimensions, TLS, pocket LiDAR, and tape measure consistently indicated that all measurements satisfied the specified tolerance limits.

Table 4. Compliance checking results for rebar positions and concrete dimensions.

	Rebar Position: Compliance	Rebar Position: Non-compliance
TLS	S1, S3, S4 , S5, S6, S10, S11, L2	S0, S2, S7, S8, S9, S12, S13, L0, L1, L3
PL	S1, S5, S6, S10, S11, L2	S0, S2, S3, S4 , S7, S8, S9, S12, S13, L0, L1, L3

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the feasibility of pocket LiDAR as a practical tool for dimensional quality control of precast concrete elements by benchmarking its performance against TLS and traditional tape measurements. The results demonstrate that pocket LiDAR significantly outperforms tape measurements in rebar position detection, achieving substantially lower RMSE values and providing more consistent measurements. While TLS remains the most accurate method, pocket LiDAR showed sufficient accuracy to capture critical geometric and positional information within acceptable tolerance ranges for many QC applications. In particular, its ability to detect rebar displacement with reasonable precision highlights its potential for supporting automated inspection workflows. However, discrepancies observed in borderline compliance cases indicate that pocket LiDAR may still have limitations when measurements approach tolerance thresholds. Additionally, reduced point density and sensitivity to rebar surface conditions may affect performance in more complex geometries. Overall, pocket LiDAR presents a promising, cost-effective alternative to TLS for rapid and automated QC in precast construction. Future work should focus on improving reconstruction accuracy, integrating automated feature extraction, and validating performance across more complex structural elements such as MSE wall panels.

5. REFERENCES

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